

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

EVALUATE THE EFFECT OF THE COVID-19 EPIDEMIC ON RESIDENCY IN OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY TRAINING PROGRAM IN PAKISTAN

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Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Aim: To assess the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the obstetrics and gynecology residency preparing program in Pakistan.

Methods: This was a cross-sectional study designed to evaluate the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the residency preparation program in obstetrics and gynecology in Pakistan. A 48-question online study was submitted and secretly completed by the occupants after tolerating informed consent. Greetings to the online study were sent to all Pakistani obstetrics and gynecology occupants. Those who were on maternity leave at the time of the survey were avoided. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. Residents received information about their regular pre-pandemic COVID-19 action, and to report the decrease in their clinical practice. They also received information on the psychological effects of COVID-19 on their clinical practice.

Results: 939 Pakistani occupants in obstetrics and gynecology were welcomed for this synthesis study. Four hundred of them, 79 (53%), completed the study and were retained for the examination. 300 and 87 (82.5%) were female and 87 (19.9%) were male. The age of the occupants increased from 25 to 42 years. In 71.8% (343/479) of the cases, the occupants worked in a COVID-19 reference hospital. 100 and 84 out of 76 (38.6%) residents were tested by RT-PCR on examples of nasal and pharyngeal swabs, and of these 14/188 (7.6%) were positive for SARS VOC-2. Regarding the use of Personal Defense Equipment (PPE), 269 (57.3%) responded that they had obtained a satisfactory gadget, while 382 (78.7%) felt that they were very well informed about the anticipation and conventions of the Board of Directors. 300 and 31 occupants (67.8%) responded that they had supervised VIDOC-positive patients-19. For 54.7% of the occupants surveyed, the general readiness to move decreased mainly during the COVID-19 scourge. A decrease of 38% was observed in 32.6% of cases, while a total suspension of preparation was observed in 8.6% of cases. In 88.5% of cases, the decrease was caused by work reorganization. Nervousness about the future of the experts was the cause of 84% of the cases, and 58% of them felt that their preparation was irreversibly compromised.

Conclusion: Among Pakistani occupants in obstetrics and gynecology, COVID-19 pandemic was related with a huge preparing weakness.

Keywords: COVID-19 epidemic, obstetrics and gynecology, Pakistan.

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Please cite this article in press Abbas et al, Evaluate The Effect Of The Covid-19 Epidemic On Residency In Obstetrics And Gynecology Training Program In Pakistan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Epic Coronavirus 2019, or Severe Acute Respiratory Coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), is a recent infection that responds to COVID-19 [1]. The coronavirus is linked to impaired well-being, financial and psychological outcomes. Among all nations, Pakistan has been strongly influenced, with more than 225,700 cases and more than 30,000 passages as of early May [2]. Hence, as a result of the forced closure, public gatherings were banned and most movements were confined [3]. The medical services system was also overhauled, with elective surgeries and the majority of outpatient arrangements delayed. Many patients will experience the long-term effects of COVID-19, with an increasing number of missed tests, difficulties related to health conditions due to delayed treatment and increased nervousness [4]. In addition, residency training projects may be affected by the COVID-19 scourge, while limited information has been disseminated to date. The purpose of this review was to assess the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the residency training program in obstetrics and gynecology in Pakistan [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This was a cross-sectional study planned to evaluate the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the residency preparation program in obstetrics and gynecology in Pakistan. A 45-question online study was sent through the Pakistani Obstetrics and Gynecology Trainee Network and was completed without names by the occupants after receiving informed consent. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. The neighborhood BRI provided the survey for the Moral Audit. The request for the online examination was sent on 28 April 2020 to all Pakistani residents in obstetrics and gynecology, with little regard to sexual orientation. In Pakistan, the duration of the internship preparation program in Obstetrics and Gynecology is five years. Candidates from the first to the fifth year of the preparation program are welcome to take the exam. Those who were on maternity leave at the time of the examination have been excluded. The online study consisted of three different parts. In the first part, sectoral information was collected, such as sexual orientation, age and year of residence. In addition, occupants were provided with information on their regular movements prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In particular, they received information on the number of elective systems each month, with major and minor detail tasks, and on the ambulatory hub. In the second part of the study, the inhabitants were approached to report the decrease in their clinical practice (0 = not so much/3; 2/3; 3/3 = total suspension of practice), and

the educational action. In the last part of the study, the inhabitants were questioned about the mental effect of COVID-19 on their clinical way of treating patients and on their thoughts about their professional future. The statistical review was conducted using the Statistical Package for Sociologies (SPSS) v. 19.0 (IBM Inc.). The information is presented as means with standard deviation, or as a number (rate). Separate overviews were determined for the socio-demographic qualities. Survey results were also examined by sexual orientation of occupants, year of residence, COVID-19 energy and number of occupants in the middle using a strategic relapse survey.

RESULTS:

900 and 33 Pakistani residents in obstetrics; in addition, gynecology, from all 41 residency training programs in Pakistan, was welcomed by e-mail. Of the 930 occupants received, 479 (51.3%) completed the examination. 308 and 87 (87.7%) of the respondents were female and 89 (16.9%) were male. The age of the occupants increased from 26 to 49, with a normal age of 29. In 72% of cases (344/476), the occupants worked in a VIDOC-19 reference hospital. One hundred and eighty-four (38.6%) occupants were subjected to continuous transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) testing on nasal and pharyngeal swab specimens, and of these, 12/184 (9.78%) were positive for VOC-2 SARS. 100 and 95 out of 476 (41.1%) occupants were tested for SARS-VOC-2 immunization with either a chemiluminescence immunoassay investigation or a rapid IgM-IgG immunization test. With respect to the use of Personal Defense Equipment (PPE), 267 (56.1%) responded that they had obtained a satisfactory gadget, while 379 (79.6%) felt that they were very well informed about the counterattack and board conventions. 300 and 31 occupants (69.6%) responded that they had supervised patients who were VIDOC-positive-19. For 54.7% of respondents, overall preparedness decreased (2/3 decrease) during the COVID-19 pandemic. While 19 out of 476 (3.8%) responded without reporting a decrease in preparedness, a decrease of 33% was reported in 31.4% of cases, while a complete suspension of preparedness was observed in 9.9% of cases. In 89.3% of cases, the decrease was caused by the reorganization of work teams, while 8.2% and 2.5% decreased their action due to the clinical solution or compulsory isolation, individually. The territories generally included in this decrease are those identified with elective surgeries, with 39.7% and 40.4% of occupants detailing absolute suspension of major and minor conservative exercises, individually (Fig. 1).

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

DISCUSSION:

This cross-sectional study was designed to assess the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the residency preparation program in obstetrics and gynecology in Pakistan [6]. To our knowledge, this may be the first study evaluating the effect of COVID-19 on the occupants preparing for residency in obstetrics and gynecology [7-9]. The findings of the review indicated that among Pakistani occupants in obstetrics and gynecology, the COVID-19 pandemic was linked to a critical weakness in preparedness. This investigation was limited by the cross-sectional study design. We included only Pakistani occupants, so the information from this review may not be relevant to individual nations [10].

CONCLUSION:

In summary, among the Pakistani occupants, the COVID-19 pandemic had an impressive negative effect on the obstetrics and gynecology residency preparation program. Our findings can be used to find new answers to limit the effect of COVID-19 on the nature of residency preparation programs. New authoritative methodologies are important to limit the inadequacies of preparation. While they are not virtually identical to the viable movement, there may be distinct imaginative arrangements available, such as online practice questions, remote coordination including telemedicine center occupants, the use of testing systems, and the use of careful recording.

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